

WORK AS THE MAIN CATEGORY OF ERGONOMICS

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Annotation: In the data of the articles, Economics, one of the main disciplines in the field of labor protection, is analyzed. And also the main methods of ergonomic analysis of the elements of the "man - machine" systems are considered: dimensional characteristics of a person,

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To ensure optimal working conditions, the greatest convenience in handling machines and devices, many scientists from such different disciplines as biology, medicine, and mathematics were involved. they were engaged in the field of labor activity of people. studied their ability, as well as psychological and physical resources.

So, in the fifties of the last century, a new science, ergonomics, began to appear. the basis of its study was the capabilities of workers, the correct equipment of the working environment and the creation of the most convenient tools for work.

Ergonomics is a discipline that comprehensively studies a person or a group of people in the specific conditions of modern production. the emergence of ergonomics is associated with the enormous technological progress that we can observe in the last century. it was formed at the junction of many sciences related

to man. this is psychology, and physiology, and hygiene, and anatomy, as well as a number of technical sciences. when designing new equipment, it is necessary to take into account the human factor: the features and capabilities of the person who will use this equipment. since due to the complication of technology and an increase in its cost, the "price" of a human error can become quite high. therefore, the requirements for various types of labor activity must be coordinated not by one science, but by several.

What can be called the main goals of ergonomics? this, of course, is the desire for a high coefficient of efficiency of the "man-equipment-environment" system, the maximum provision of labor safety, the creation of optimal conditions for the development of an employee in the labor process.

When we talk about ergonomics tasks, we are talking about a set of tasks. to solve one of the most important tasks, optimization of working conditions, the features and capabilities of workers at various levels are studied, the results obtained are taken into account for further design of the workplace. Also, ergonomics has recently been separated by the problem of rehabilitation of people who have lost their ability to work.

The main objectives of the development of this discipline, we can include: the development of a theory of designing the worker's activity, the compilation and testing of hypotheses about the prospects for labor and related technical systems, various information processes: processing, data evaluation. the object of ergonomics is the "man-technology-environment" system, and the subject is the labor process of a person with his interaction with technology under the influence of various environments.

Ergonomics is a field of knowledge that comprehensively studies the labor activity of people in such a system as "man-technology-environment" in order to ensure the efficiency, safety and some comfort of human labor activity. Because of this, studies of ergonomics are directly based on the laws of both mental and

physiological processes, and study the interactions and characteristics of a person with a tool and objects of labor.

At its present stage, ergonomics is an integral science of labor activity, effectively increasing labor, namely labor activity by optimizing working conditions. As for labor efficiency, we are talking about high labor productivity and a positive impact on the personality of the worker, his satisfaction.

It is ergonomics that includes solving problems of optimizing labor activity, and also contributes to labor protection, labor safety and occupational health. The ergonomic aspect of labor safety is solved with the intervention of psychology.

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When an information base, communications, workplace design are created, then there is a reflection on the production process and relationships. As for the development of uniform standards and criteria for labor activity, safety values and a minimum of emergencies, as well as the optimization of working conditions, are very important for each profession.

If we consider the definition of A. Marshall, then labor is any mental and physical effort undertaken in part or in whole in order to achieve any result, not counting the satisfaction received directly from the work itself [1, p.26]. An integrated approach, which is characteristic of ergonomics, will allow you to get the most comprehensive idea of labor, the labor process and the wide possibilities for its improvement.

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It is this approach that is of particular value for the scientific organization of labor, where the practical implementation of specific measures is preceded by a scientific analysis of the labor process and conditions of implementation. As for practical measures, they are based on the achievements of modern science and practice.

Everyone knows that man is the main and most complex element of production. If you do not know the nature of man and do not know how to use it, then this will lead to significant losses, both social and economic. It is not in vain that the world community has come to the conclusion that the main reserves of production efficiency lie precisely in people, and it is there that it directs all its efforts.

Ergonomics asks questions such as why a person gets tired, why he reduces his ability to work, why he makes mistakes even in elementary things, why it

takes time to rest. If a person knows all these patterns, then he will be able to help organize production. Namely, to increase labor productivity, reduce fatigue and dissatisfaction with work.

As you know, labor productivity leads to a positive financial result, and as far as job satisfaction is concerned, this leads to staff stability, to a certain dedication in production. In the system called "man-technology-environment", one of the central areas of research and design of labor activity is the workplace of a person.

It is the workplace that acts as the smallest integral unit of production, which is characterized by such elements of labor as the subject, means and subject of labor. It is necessary to define the workplace in such a way that it provides the working person with those conditions that are beneficial, successful and safe for the course of labor activity. The organization of labor is the result of a certain system of measures for the functioning, as well as for the spatial placement of both the main and auxiliary means of labor in order to ensure optimal conditions for the labor process.

The main means of labor are equipment. With the help of equipment, a person will be able to perform labor operations. It can be machine tools, various stands or industrial robots. Auxiliary means of labor can be divided into 2 types: technological equipment and organizational equipment. As for technological equipment, it is in it that the main production equipment is effectively operated at the workplace. For example, a sharpening tool, adjustment, control or repair.

About organizational equipment, we can say that it effectively ensures the organization of labor, while creating convenience and safety in operation, in the maintenance of the main production equipment. For example, a device for transporting or storing objects of labor, or a means of signaling, communications, work furniture, and so on [2, p. 48].

If we consider in the general case how a person and tools interact, then we

can see that in the process of labor they express the content of labor and the composition of labor functions, namely the totality of actions performed by a person. It is possible to single out various human functions that occur directly in the production process. Firstly, it is an energy function, where the worker puts the tool into action.

Secondly, it is a technological function, where the worker connects the tool of labor and the object of labor, thereby changing the parameters of labor. Thirdly, it is a control and regulatory function, which is associated with monitoring, controlling movement, changing the object of labor, as well as adjusting tools and monitoring functioning. Further, fourthly, it is a managerial function.

It is associated with the preparation of production, as well as with the implementation of the production process. With the help of scientific and technological progress, humanity is freed from various energy and technological functions, and as a result, the main functions are management and control and regulation.

The person, as it were, withdraws from participation in the technological process, performs preparatory operations. Here, the tool of labor serves as a means of expanding human capabilities, as well as developing his creative initiative. As for the system called "man-machine-environment", the effectiveness of this system can be directly determined by the ergonomic requirements for the tool, which, in turn, can establish the ratio of the properties and characteristics of the tools, individually or in combination, taking into account both technological equipment, and organizational equipment, manifested in the process of labor activity.

Ergonomic requirements for tools can be set for elements that are already associated with a person in the process of performing labor actions, for example, in the process of repair, operation, or transportation, storage, regulation,

installation, and so on. These requirements for labor tools should be established in accordance with the physiological, anthropometric, psychophysiological, and psychological properties of a person. You also need to take into account sanitary and hygienic requirements in order to maintain human health and achieve a high degree of labor efficiency.

The production environment itself is an interconnected set of factors and elements of the environment that surrounds a person in the process of his work, and also has an impact on human health, on the amount of energy costs in general and on specific actions, namely their implementation. The well-being of the employee, his working capacity, productivity, as well as his emotional state are of great importance.

Ergonomics begins to realize that it enters a new development when it itself becomes a necessary and main component of planning, developing projects that are related to people and their work.

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